

Research Article

Home, Work, Play: Design Thinking to Promote Socio-Spatial Well-Being for Urban and Rural Hybrid-Working Generation Rent

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Abstract: “Generation Rent” reflects growing housing insecurity among young adults in England, particularly those navigating hybrid working arrangements. This study examines the socio-spatial challenges experienced of urban and rural hybrid-working Generation Rent. An embedded mixed-methods approach was used, combining an online survey of 193 participants aged 18–35 using the Warwick–Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale (WEMWBS) and focus groups within a design thinking framework. Two case studies were analysed: Bungay (Suffolk), representing rural young adults living with family, and Clerkenwell (London), representing private renters. Quantitative results showed no statistically significant difference in well-being between these groups. Qualitative findings revealed rural participants reported limited amenities, long commutes, and restricted workspace options, while urban renters experienced housing insecurity, limited space, and both reporting blurred work–home boundaries. The study proposes “third places” integrating co-working, leisure, and social aspects.

Implications: Socio-spatial conditions influence the everyday experiences of hybrid-working young adults across both urban and rural contexts. For practitioners in urban design and mental health, understanding these relationships may inform future planning and design approaches that respond to changing patterns of hybrid-working.

Keywords: Generation Rent; Hybrid working; Socio-spatial well-being; Third places; Private rented sector; Urban-rural; Social infrastructure; Housing insecurity

1. Introduction

A prominent trend in contemporary housing discourse is the emergence of *Generation Rent*, a term used to describe younger cohorts facing significant challenges in accessing homeownership (Timperley, 2020). The need and desire for a stable space for domestic, work, and creative purposes is not merely a contemporary concern. In “A Room of One’s Own” (Woolf, 1929), 20th-century author Virginia Woolf articulated the consequences of domestic and work-related spatial inequalities. Mohamed (2022) draws on the reflections of Woolf (1929) and presents a case for the consequences of precarious, transient, and impermanent housing options on well-being. Housing options for young adults are shaped by structural constraints and cultural stigma. In England, homeownership is constructed as a marker of adulthood and financial success (McKee et al., 2017; Howard, 2024). Financial constraints, limited access to social housing, and shifting socio-economic paradigms have contributed to the prolonged transition into stable housing (Bano, 2024; Hoolachan et al., 2016). The purpose of this research is to synthesise interdisciplinary primary and secondary research to understand the challenges experienced by the demographic labelled Generation Rent who have a hybrid working arrangement with their employer, impacting socio-spatial well-being.

1.1. Generation Rent: Tenant and Precariat

The subgroups of Generation Rent have been identified as the “Tenants”, “Precariat”, “Second Generation Owner”, and the “Delayed Buyer” (Howard, 2024). This research focuses on “Tenants” living in the Private Rented Sector (PRS) and the “Precariat”, defined in

this research as young adults living with family or friends. The two groups are selected because they experience the highest degrees of housing insecurity, limited spatial autonomy, and exposure to uncertainty; Unlike “Second Generation Owners,” who possess intergenerational safety nets, or “Delayed Buyers,” whose precarity is often transitional and asset-oriented, Tenants and the Precariat remain dependent on insecure rental markets or extended co-residence arrangements (Howard, 2024). It is important to note that these groups can fluctuate between renting privately and co-residence with family in response to lease termination, employment precarity, rent increase, or working relocations.

Social fragmentation describes neighbourhood conditions where social relationships between residents are weak or dispersed, limiting opportunities for interaction and reducing levels of social cohesion (Grigoroglou et al., 2020). Urban areas, characterised by higher levels of social fragmentation, tend to be populated by younger adults who live alone and rent in the private sector (Grigoroglou et al., 2020). Additionally, rural Generation Rent experience limited social opportunities and employment stability, often migrating to cities (Hoolachan et al., 2016). While migration for Generation Rent can fluctuate between urban and rural locations, social fragmentation can occur in both contexts.

London has one of the largest private rented sectors with the most expensive rents in England (Office for National Statistics, 2025b). Escalating housing costs in the Private Rented Sector (PRS) marginalises younger and less affluent tenants in cities such as London, where employment opportunities are concentrated (Le Gales and Pierson, 2019). However, the expansion of hybrid-work has contributed to the migration toward suburban and rural areas, loosening the tether between employment and city centres in the pursuit of and improved quality of life and more affordable living and housing costs (Zenkteler et al., 2019). Hybrid-work is defined as the arrangement in which employees divide work between conventional workplaces and remote settings, reconfiguring boundaries between rest and labour (Vartiainen and Vanharanta, 2023). The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated this structural shift in the spatial organisation of work across multiple sectors (Zenkteler, Foth and Hearn, 2022; Hopkins and Bardoel, 2023), prompting a re-evaluation of housing as spaces for leisure, work, social interaction, and exercise, particularly for family households and shared accommodation where spatial and social constraints were evident (Özer & Jones, 2022)

1.2. Socio-Spatial Well-Being and Third Places

The socio-spatial perspective examines the relationship between social processes and spatial environments (Lefebvre, 1991). Socio-spatial well-being refers to how built environments and social relationships influence mental and emotional well-being, highlighting the role of planning, urban design, and policy in shaping environments that support social interaction and everyday life (Rajendran et al., 2020). This provides a framework (as seen in Figure 1) for interdisciplinary research to inform holistic approaches for planning, policy, urban design.

Figure 1. The Socio-Spatial Framework for Inclusive Health and Well-Being.

In contexts where domestic environments cannot adequately support hybrid working, accessible third places may play a role in providing alternative spaces for work, social interaction, and community engagement. Ray Oldenburg’s concept of “third places”, the communal spaces distinct from home (first place) and work (second place) (Oldenburg, 1989), has regained relevance in the context of remote and hybrid working; Oldenburg

(1989) identifies third places such as libraries, parks, cafés and community centres as vital nodes of social connection that prevent isolation. Building on this, Zenkteler (et al., 2019) found that home-based workers strongly prefer living in neighbourhoods designed to support functions for work and leisure and proposed the intervention of a "third place". Furthermore, policy responses play an important role in shaping opportunities for social connection and well-being, particularly in rural locations. Irish government policy has supported co-working hubs to address isolation and population decline in rural areas, with the motivation to retain or attract young populations (Wall and Crowe, 2024). Austerity policies have been linked to declining mental and physical well-being (Stuckler et al., 2017). In England, these measures have also contributed to the loss of third places such as libraries and leisure centres, key forms of social infrastructure that support community cohesion, especially during crises (Bogue and Ouillon, 2023).

1.3. Bungay and Clerkenwell

Bungay and the Saints, located in Suffolk (England), was selected as the rural case study representing Generation Rent living with family, conceptualised in this research as the "Precariat". The area is characterised by an ageing population, high levels of homeownership (68%), limited private rental supply, and reduced transport and infrastructure typical of rural England (Office for National Statistics, 2025a; Waveney District Council, 2018).

Clerkenwell in the London Borough of Islington (England) was selected as the urban case study representing Generation Rent in the Private Rented Sector (PRS). The primary age group are aged between 20-39 years old (42%) and has a significant population of households renting privately (Office for National Statistics, 2021). Furthermore, 94% live in a "Flat, maisonette or apartment" (Office for National Statistics, 2021). This location is chosen to research the challenges of young adults renting privately in London (Le Gales and Pierson, 2019).

Examining these contrasting contexts enables the study to explore the challenges experiences of hybrid-working Generation Rent in urban and rural England.

1.4. Research Gaps, Aims and Questions

Few studies explore how hybrid-working Generation Rent experience spatial constraints across both urban and rural contexts, or how planning and design interventions may support their everyday needs for work, social interaction, and leisure to promote well-being. Addressing this gap is important as hybrid working continues to reshape relationships between home, work, and leisure.

The aims of the study are to examine the socio-spatial challenges faced by hybrid-working Generation Rent, using the case studies of Bungay (rural) and Clerkenwell (urban). The research questions for this study are:

1. How do the socio-spatial challenges identified impact urban and rural hybrid-working Generation Rent?
2. What spatial interventions can support the socio-spatial well-being of hybrid-working Generation Rent?

2. Methods

Figure 2. Methodology Flowchart

This study adopts an embedded mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative methods. The pragmatic research paradigm (Duram, 2010) was used in this research to allow a holistic approach to understanding and addressing the complex nature of the research problem. A combination of data science and design thinking techniques were employed (Figure 2). The design thinking framework is a human-centred approach to problem-solving comprising of five non-linear stages; *Empathise*, *Define*, *Ideate*, *Prototype*, and *Test* (Interaction Design Foundation, 2023). This research design used focus groups, an online survey, and data science methods to explore socio-spatial challenges for urban and rural Generation Rent.

2.1. Online Survey

An online survey was conducted using Microsoft Forms. The survey was advertised using the Facebook group 'Landlord and Tenants UK'. The criteria for respondents stated that they must be 18-35 years old and live in England. Participants were asked to provide the region and local authority they live in. A total of 193 respondents answered questions about the spaces they associate with 'home', 'work', and 'play'. The concluding questions included the Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale (WEMWBS) (Warwick Medical School, 2021b) to measure participants' well-being.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Survey Respondents (n = 193)

Characteristic	Category	n	%
Living arrangement	Private Rented Sector (PRS)	74	38.3
	Living with Family (LWF)	119	61.7
Gender	Woman	112	58.0
	Man	81	42.0
Age group	18-24	94	48.7
	25-29	53	27.5
	30-35	46	23.8
Ethnicity	White	145	75.1
	Asian / Asian British	18	9.3
	Black / Black British	12	6.2
	Mixed / Multiple ethnic groups	10	5.2
	Other ethnic groups	8	4.1
Occupation	Full-time employment	92	47.7
	Part-time employment	28	14.5
	Student	51	26.4
	Self-employed	9	4.7
	Other	13	6.7

The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale (WEMWBS) (Warwick Medical School, 2021b) was chosen as the well-being metric for this study because of its comprehensive approach to measuring mental well-being. Unlike other scales that may focus solely on negative aspects of mental health, such as anxiety or depression, this scale allows the research to capture the emotional and psychological aspects of young adults. The scores of each participant were calculated by converting the statements to a scale between 1 to 5 and creating a score based on the total of the numbers (Warwick Medical School, 2021a).

Data science techniques were used to visualise the primary data from the online survey. The survey responses were exported as a Microsoft Excel sheet, and the data was cleaned. Python programming language was used on Google Colab for statistical analysis.

The latitude and longitude based on each survey respondent's local authority and rural-urban classification were added. The research defines rural and urban based on the 2011 Rural-Urban Classification in England (Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2013).

2.2. Case Study Locations

The chosen geographical areas for the site designs are described as Middle Layer Super Output Areas (MSOAs) within local authorities, comprising of smaller geographical areas named Lower Layer Super Output Areas (LSOAs) (Office for National Statistics, n.d.).

Bungay and the Saints (MSOA) is defined as a Rural Town and Fringe and Clerkenwell (MSOA) is defined as Urban with Major Conurbation (Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2021). The data has been synthesised using survey data that applies the 2011 Rural Urban Classification (Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2013). An in-person and digital site analysis on took place for the Clerkenwell and Bungay sites using ArcGIS.

2.3. Focus Groups

Participants for the focus groups were recruited using LinkedIn and Facebook groups 'Landlord and Tenants UK' and 'That Bungay Page (Formerly "The Friendly Bungay Page")'.

Two focus groups were conducted online using Zoom video calling during the *Empathise* stage. Digital activities for focus groups were conducted using the digital collaboration platforms Miro and Canva for 18-35-year-old participants in Bungay and Greater London. The focus groups were transcribed using Otter.ai software. The participants in the first focus group included four former Bungay and the Saints residents aged 18-35 currently renting privately in the London Borough of Islington. Additionally, four participants were 18-35-year-olds living with family members in Bungay. Digital activities were implemented including the 'Rose, Thorn, Bud' exercise (Ma, 2021), emotion mapping (Priyanka, 2020), and digital photo collages (Interaction Design Foundation, 2022).

The second focus group included an additional three participants who work as a town planner, housing developer, and landlord in the private rental sector. Furthermore, two participants over 35 years old residing in Clerkenwell and Bungay were included in the focus group. The specific site locations for the urban and rural "third place" designs were chosen during the *Define* stage of research. The "third place" initial prototypes were designed on Sims 4 during the second focus group with participants and in the third focus group, where the design was tested virtually using the simulation software.

A thematic analysis was then conducted using the data collected from the initial two focus groups. Furthermore, empathy maps and journey maps outputs were created. A final focus group was conducted during the *Test* phase to evaluate and provide feedback on the final prototypes.

The focus group participants informed consent was obtained through written consent forms completed online. Participant confidentiality remained throughout the research in all methods applied. Data was anonymised and stored securely in password-protected files at the London Interdisciplinary School, according to LIS guidelines, on the university network. Consent forms and other sensitive data were retained securely and only accessible to the researcher. Raw data was not shared externally, and participants could withdraw at any time without consequences.

3. Results

3.1. *Empathise and Define*

3.1.1 Rural and Living with Family (LWF) Generation Rent

The results from the Thematic Analysis presented that focus group participants in rural areas valued tranquillity and proximity to nature yet reported challenges including limited local amenities, social isolation, and a lack of cultural and recreational spaces, as seen in Table 2.

Some participants have a strong family connection at home but may need help with privacy and workspace variety; young people reported emotional support but also highlighted interpersonal challenges such as infantilisation and family conflict. Some described receiving emotional support but reported limited privacy and restricted workspace variety. Rural participants noted that third places closed early, often before their workday had finished.

Participants described having home-centric routines with limited access to third spaces. Rural participants face long and expensive commutes to their employers' workspaces in cities such as Norwich and London. Rural participants perceived fewer social and professional opportunities compared to urban areas.

Table 2. Thematic Analysis: Rural Generation Rent (Living with Family [LWF])

Theme	Theme Code	Description	Participant Examples
Rural Living Environment	Connection to Nature	Participants valued tranquillity and access to natural landscapes for well-being.	"I appreciate having so much access to nature after work."
Rural Living Environment	Family Support	Living with family provided emotional and financial stability.	"Living with family can feel more like living I'm living in an actual "home" compared to renting."
Rural Living Environment	Limited Privacy and Independence	Participants reported reduced autonomy and feelings of infantilisation when living with family.	"Living with my family and working at home makes me feel like a child again."
Work and Mobility	Long and Expensive Commutes	Participants described commuting long distances to cities such as Norwich or London for work.	"I travel to work for so many hours in to London when my boss asks me too which gets expensive."
Work and Mobility	Limited Workspace Variety in Family Home	Participants reported difficulty finding quiet workspaces or alternative working environments.	"Finding a quiet place to work without interruptions is nearly impossible because I live with lots of people."
Access to Amenities	Limited Local Amenities	Participants highlighted a lack of cultural, social, and recreational facilities in rural areas.	"I have to travel 40 minutes to Norwich to go to the cinema or visit an art gallery."
Access to Amenities	Early Closing Third Spaces	Local cafés, pubs, and social spaces were reported to close early.	"Cafés and libraries close before the workday has finished."
Social Life	Rural Social Isolation	Participants described fewer social and professional opportunities compared with urban areas.	"There's not much of community for people my age since school has ended."

3.1.2. Urban and Living in the Private Rental Sector (PRS) Generation Rent

Urban participants viewed their living spaces as temporary and devoid of personal significance due to the transient nature of renting. The challenges they associated living in the PRS included housing insecurity, high living costs (transportation and housing), and limited personal space in co-residence flats, as presented in Table 3.

Participants described having challenges with their landlord such as rental costs being increased at the end of their tenancy, causing feelings of stress deciding to return to live with family and commute, continuing living in the same rental and pay more, or find a new place to live.

Table 3. Thematic Analysis: Urban Generation Rent (Living in the Private Rented Sector [PRS])

Theme	Theme Code	Description	Participant Examples
Housing Conditions	Temporary Nature of Renting	Participants described rental housing as temporary and lacking emotional attachment.	"I feel like sometimes the place I live in London doesn't feel like home."
Housing Conditions	Housing Insecurity	Participants reported stress caused by rent increases and tenancy uncertainty.	"There is such a lack of control over your choices about how long you live in your tenancy for and when it will change."
Housing Conditions	Limited Personal Space	Shared accommodation reduced privacy and personal space.	"I try and make my bedroom feel like a sanctuary after the workday has ended."
Shared Living	Flatmate Interpersonal Challenges	Participants described tension with flatmates compared with living with family.	"It's really difficult to find a balance when you're working in the same space where you live, especially in a shared flat."
Work Environments	Blurred Work/Home Boundaries	Remote work made it difficult to separate work and leisure in shared accommodation.	"It's hard to find a balance when you're working in the same space where you live."
Urban Accessibility	Access to Third Workspaces	Participants benefited from proximity to cafés, libraries, and co-working spaces.	"Some of the libraries I go to work are so loud but at least it's a free space."
Financial Constraints	High Cost of Living	High rent and transport costs limited opportunities for leisure and social activities.	"In London it's so expensive to socialise when everything adds up."
Social Life	Urban Isolation	Participants reported feelings of isolation despite living in dense cities.	"It can be hard to maintain friendships ."

Urban participants noted that the high cost of living constrains opportunities for leisure and social activities after rent and travel expenses are paid, perpetuating feelings of isolation and disconnection from friends.

Participants also reported experiences of isolation when working remotely and difficulties finding quiet or private workspaces within shared rental housing. When commuting into their employer's workspace, participants felt they benefited from shorter commutes and access to cafés, libraries, and co-working spaces, which supported more flexible working routines. Participants described their limited living space in shared accommodation reduced privacy and the ability to maintain clear boundaries between leisure and work. Furthermore, these participants felt like they had more interpersonal challenges with flat mates than living with their own families.

3.1.3. Survey Results and Data Analysis

Using Python, well-being scores (WEMWBS) of respondents aged 18-35 were analysed by living arrangement (Living with Family [LWF] and Private Rented Sector [PRS]) to explore whether housing tenure alone was associated with differences in mental well-being.

Figure 3. Boxplot: Well-Being Scores for Living with Family (LWF) and the Private Rented Sector (PRS)

Figure 3 visualises the distribution of well-being scores across living arrangements. The horizontal lines inside each box denote the median well-being score of 41.0 for the LWF group and 42.5 for the PRS group. The average well-being scores were similar between the two groups, with the PRS group having a mean score of 42.5 and the LWF group having a slightly lower mean score of 41.3. While PRS respondents display a marginally higher central tendency, the interquartile ranges indicate comparable distributions across both groups.

Table 4. Hypothesis Test Results: Well-Being Scores by Living Arrangement.

T-Statistic	P-Value
-1.471	0.143

In Table 4, the t-statistic (the ratio that compares the difference between the means of two groups to the variability of the data) is displayed. Furthermore, the p-value (the probability of observing a test statistic as extreme as, or more extreme than, the observed value under the null hypothesis) is presented. The t-statistic of -1.471 and the p-value of 0.143 suggest that the difference in mean well-being scores between the two groups (those living with family and those in the private rented sector) is not statistically significant.

Figure 4. Trends in Well-Being Scores.

Trends in Well-Being Scores by Age, Rural-Urban Classification, and Living Arrangement

Figure 4 illustrates trends in well-being across age, urban-rural classification, and living arrangement. Rather than indicating a singular tenure effect, the patterns suggest that well-being may be shaped by the interaction of spatial context and living arrangement. Respondents in “Urban with Major Conurbation” classifications display relatively stable and

moderately higher well-being scores across age groups, with both LWF and PRS respondents clustering within a similar range. There is greater variability observed in “Urban with City and Town” and rural classifications. In rural contexts, particularly “Mainly Rural” and “Largely Rural,” well-being scores appear more dispersed across age groups, indicating greater fluctuation. This variability is visible among younger respondents and those living with family, whereas PRS respondents in urban classifications demonstrate comparatively more consistency.

3.2. Ideate, Prototype, and Test

3.2.1. Bungay Designs & Recommendations

Co-working spaces were designed with comfortable seating such as sofas and armchairs. The second floor was divided with separate meeting rooms and noise-proof spaces for solitude work and video calls. Moreover, the digital prototype (Figure 5) was seen as an opportunity to enhance social integration through communal activities, rooftop gardens, and pop-up events with the intent to bring together different generations rather than Generation Rent only.

Figure 5. Bungay Prototype & Floorplan

Improving public transport connections was a significant concern for participants in Bungay. As presented in Figure 6, participants suggested the introduction of shuttle services to train stations, and the addition of more bus routes for surrounding villages in Bungay and Wainford to facilitate access to the development and enhanced bus connectivity between areas.

Figure 6. Bungay Site Analysis and Recommendations

Participants emphasised the value of the of fitness, socialising, and leisure within one site, seen as a significant advantage for its potential to increase accessibility to leisure and social spaces after work hours. Similarly, to the Bungay development, the Clerkenwell development features co-working spaces with a variety of seating.

Noise emerged as a major concern for the Clerkenwell mixed-use development during the Test stage of research. Participants underscored the need for effective soundproofing and zoning within the building to maintain a sense of calm and productivity amidst the various activities housed within the building.

Figure 8. Clerkenwell Prototype & Floorplan

In addition to the final design for Clerkenwell (Figure 9), a planning partnership between rail companies (such as National Rail) and local hotels or Airbnb hosts to offer discounted rates for individuals in need of temporary accommodation near Barbican station and Liverpool Street has been proposed, where these individuals are likely to rely on commuting to work via the aforementioned stations. The collaboration between transportation services and accommodation providers were discussed for young adults facing unstable living situations, such as those between leases or residing with family members, by creating a network of hubs between towns and cities.

Figure 9. Clerkenwell Site Analysis and Recommendations

4. Discussion

This study examined the socio-spatial challenges experienced by hybrid-working members of Generation Rent and explored how these challenges differ across urban and rural contexts.

The quantitative analysis of WEMWBS scores found no statistically significant difference in mean well-being between respondents living with family (mean = 41.3) and those renting privately (mean = 42.6) ($t = -1.471$, $p = 0.143$). This suggests that housing tenure alone does not explain variations in well-being among Generation Rent. Respondents in “Urban with Major Conurbation” classifications showed relatively consistent well-being scores across age groups, while rural classifications displayed greater variability, although these patterns do not establish causal relationships.

Participants in Bungay valued the tranquillity of rural living and the emotional support associated with living with family. However, these benefits were often accompanied by reduced privacy, limited workspace variety, and tensions between domestic and professional roles when working from home. This reflects broader discussions about the spatial implications of hybrid working, where domestic environments increasingly accommodate both work and leisure functions (Vartiainen and Vanharanta, 2023). Participants also reported limited access to cultural amenities, with cafés, libraries, and social spaces often closing early or requiring travel to nearby cities. Long commutes to employment centres such as Norwich or London were described as financially and temporally demanding. These conditions contribute to forms of rural social fragmentation, where dispersed populations and limited amenities reduce opportunities for regular social interaction (Hoolachan et al., 2016). To address these challenges, the study proposed a multi-functional third-place hub in Bungay integrating co-working spaces, social areas, and community activities. Proposed interventions included flexible workspaces, quiet rooms for focused work, and communal areas encouraging interaction. Participants also highlighted the need for improved connectivity between surrounding villages and the town centre, including shuttle buses to train stations, enhanced bus routes, and improved pedestrian access. These interventions suggest rural hubs could function as nodes linking villages, towns, and cities for hybrid workers.

Urban Generation Rent in the private rented sector faced different socio-spatial constraints. Participants in Clerkenwell described housing as temporary and characterised by rising rents, insecure tenancies, and limited domestic space. Shared accommodation often blurred boundaries between work and leisure, reflecting research linking the private rented sector to instability and reduced control over living conditions (McKee et al., 2017). Despite proximity to employment and third spaces such as cafés and libraries, participants still reported isolation, supporting the concept of social fragmentation in dense urban environments (Grigoroglou et al., 2020). Financing travel costs also limited access to leisure and social activities. To address these challenges, the study proposed a mixed-use hub in Clerkenwell combining co-working spaces, leisure facilities, and social environments. Flexible workspaces, communal areas, and fitness facilities were designed to support everyday routines for hybrid workers. Acoustic zoning and soundproofed workspaces were also proposed to balance productive work environments with social interaction. Furthermore, the intervention of affordable temporary housing to be included for those in-between tenancies.

Limitations

The research exploring the well-being and experiences of Generation Rent in England faces several limitations. Firstly, the geographic scope of the qualitative data is limited to the chosen case study areas, which may not adequately represent the diverse perspectives and experiences of young adults in other regions with different housing and planning policies. The use of self-reported data from online surveys and focus groups introduces potential biases and limitations in terms of accuracy and reliability. The sample size, while adequate for exploratory purposes, may not represent the entire Generation Rent population in England. Greater attention to participant demographics could enhance the interpretation of the findings. The sample was predominantly female (58%) and largely White (75.1%), suggesting that further examination of how gender and ethnicity influence housing experiences and access to workspaces may provide deeper insight. The absence of longitudinal data limits the understanding of the long-term implications of prolonged renting and co-residence with family on individual and societal well-being. The current study provides a snapshot of well-being and experiences, but projections and current indicators used may fail to capture the comprehensive evolution of these dynamics over time.

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